

EFFECTIVE METHODS OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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Abstract. Method is a procedure, technique, or way of doing something, especially in accordance with a definite plan. This article describes some effective methods of teaching foreign languages in educational process.

Keywords: method, foreign language, teaching process, direct method, structural method, task-based learning.

Method literally means a pursuit of knowledge, investigation, mode of prosecuting such inquiry, or system. In recent centuries it more often means a prescribed process for completing a task. A method is basically a way of doing something. The logical strategy, for illustration, is one of a number of ways of carrying out the assignment of procuring information. While most of us are familiar with the language teaching methods used in secondary education, there is a huge variety of language learning methods available. Some of them are better suited to certain learners than others. The benefits of learning a foreign language have multiplied as the world becomes more globalized, and bilingualism is now perhaps the most useful real-world skill that has ever existed, rather than just a show-off. If you are considering making an effort to learn a foreign language instead of waiting for the world to adapt to your monolingualism, then you are truly a rare breed. Growing into the impressive multilingual you aspire to be is possible with the right approach and mindset.

Learning a foreign language is learning how to truly communicate and connect with others – an extremely important life skill that can only be cultivated by interacting with people. When you master a foreign language, you can use your new superpowers: you can understand what other people are saying, recall appropriate vocabulary and grammar, and put that vocabulary and grammar into appropriate contexts. integration and feedback, all on-the-spot and complete.

Learning foreign languages is simply part of a very basic liberal arts education. Education is directed outward – out of confinement, narrowness and obscurity. Learning a foreign language and absorbing a completely new culture and worldview is the surest way to become an open-minded, understanding, and tolerant individual, and it's absolutely invaluable. Once you realize that we are all cultural beings, products of our own environments, and you recognize the cultural underpinnings of your own attitudes and behavior, then you ready to see others in a more positive light. Seeing the world from a different perspective

and understanding where you and others are coming from is a wonderful and eye-opening experience. We can see some effective methods to use during the lesson.

The Direct Method. In this method, the teaching is done entirely in the language being learned. The learner is not allowed to use his or her original language. Grammar rules are avoided and there is an emphasis on good pronunciation.

Audio-Lingual. The theory behind this method is that learning a language means acquiring habits. There is much practice of dialogues in every situation. New language is first heard and extensively drilled before being seen in its written form.

The Structural Approach. This method sees language as a complex of grammatical rules which are to be learned one at a time in a set order. So for example the verb “to be” is introduced and practiced before the present continuous tense which uses “to be” as an auxiliary. This method of learning is common in language learning apps.

Communicative Language Teaching (CLT). The focus of this method is to enable the learner to communicate effectively and appropriately in the various situations she would be likely to find herself in. The content of CLT courses are functions such as inviting, suggesting, complaining, or notions such as the expression of time, quantity, location. Much like The Structural Approach, this method is commonly used in language learning apps.

Task-based language learning. The focus of the teaching is on the completion of a task which in itself is interesting to the learners. Learners use the language they already have to complete the task and there is little correction of errors. The aim here is to highlight the importance of learning the language by making it vital to task completion.

The Natural Approach. This approach, propounded by Professor S. Krashen, stresses the similarities between learning the first and second languages. There is no correction of mistakes. Learning takes place by the students being exposed to language that is comprehensible or made comprehensible to them.

As we have learned a description of the basic principles and procedures of the most recognized and commonly used approaches and methods for teaching a second or foreign language. Each approach or method has an articulated theoretical orientation and a collection of strategies and learning activities designed to reach the specified goals and achieve the learning outcomes of the teaching and learning processes.

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